

BASIC THERMOELECTRIC PROPERTIES OF GRANULATED SILICON DOPED WITH ALKALI METAL ATOMS

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Abstract: The thermoelectric property of semiconductor materials is the formation of different energy levels in their forbidden zone, and this property of semiconductor materials is widely used in the creation of thermocouples. According to the analysis of the literature, the main thermoelectric property of the granular semiconductor material depends on the nature of the multi-layer heterogeneous environment consisting of open states or defects in two adjacent boundary areas. Under the influence of temperature, current and voltage appear due to the formation of electron-hole pairs in a heterogeneous medium. It has been shown that the formation of electron-hole pairs depends on the nature and properties of the entrance state and defects in a multilayer heterogeneous medium.

Key words: Alkali metal atoms, semiconductor materials, thermoelectric property, heterogeneous medium, electron-hole.

Introduction

Thermoelectric properties of semiconductor materials are explained by such parameters as specific thermoelectric conductivity (α) and electrical conductivity (σ), thermal conductivity (χ). Controllability of these parameters allows creating effective thermoelectric materials based on granulated silicon. In connection with these, in this work, the thermoelectric properties of granulated silicon containing alkali metal atoms were studied. To compare the obtained results, samples of granulated silicon without alkali metal atoms were used.

Figure 1 shows the dependence of thermoelectric power on temperature.

From the obtained results, it can be seen that with increasing temperature, the thermoelectric power in granulated silicon without alkali metal atoms decreases exponentially. At ~ 400 K, its value is $500 \mu\text{V}/\text{degree}$, which corresponds to the results obtained in [1, 2]. On the contrary, an increase and decrease in thermoelectric conductivity was observed in granulated silicon containing alkali metal atoms. For example, in granulated silicon containing Na atoms, the thermoelectric power increases by 1.2 times at ~ 475 K compared to its initial state at ~ 325 K, while in samples with Cs atoms added, it increases by 1.3 times at ~ 475 K compared to its initial state at ~ 325 K. then, at the next stages of temperature increase, it is stable in samples containing Na atoms, and significantly increases in samples containing Cs atoms.

Figure 1. Dependence of thermoelectric driving force on temperature:
1 – Si, 2 – Na, 3 – Cs atoms belong to the introduced granules.

The change in voltage varies in almost similar values in all samples. The current strength increases up to 30 times in granular silicon containing alkali metal atoms compared to samples without alkali metal atoms.

In our opinion, the increase of the thermoelectric power in granulated silicon containing alkali metal atoms is due to the elimination of the recombination centers manifested in the two adjacent areas of the granulated silicon by the alkali metal

atoms and the increase in the concentration of electron-hole pairs, and the decrease in the thermoelectric power.[3-6] Lix-Ou, Nax-Ou, Kx-Ou, and Csx-Ou or Lix-Vu, Nax-Vu, Kx-Vu, and Csx-Vu are the complex combination crystone states and the formation of electron-hole pairs in them. The atomization of this area changes with the formation of Lix-Ou, Nax-Ou, Kx-Ou and Csx-Ou or Lix-Vu, Nax-Vu, Kx-Vu and Csx-Vu complex compounds in two adjacent areas of granulated silicon. which, in turn, leads to a change in the electronic state and thermal conductivity of this area. In connection with these, the thermal conductivity of the samples was also studied.[7-10]

There are several methods for determining thermal conductivity, of which the Yegor and Disselhorsta methods are useful for studying the thermal conductivity of sturgeon-shaped samples. The second chapter contains information related to this method.

Knowing the electrical conductivity of the sample (σ), the voltage drop (U) in the sample, and the temperature difference (Δt), the thermal conductivity can be determined by the following expression:

$$\chi = \frac{U\sigma}{8\Delta t} \quad (1)$$

Figure 2 shows the dependence of thermal conductivity on temperature. The obtained results show that the thermal conductivity of all samples increases with increasing temperature. As the temperature increases, the thermal conductivity of granulated silicon without alkali metal atoms at ≤ 400 K is ~ 15 V $\cdot$ k/ μ K, [1] which corresponds to the results obtained in [2]. At the next stages of temperature increase, it changes to $\sim 30 \div 40$ V $\cdot$ k/mK. In the samples containing alkali metal atoms, an increase in thermal conductivity up to ~ 475 K and then a decrease was observed. For example, thermal conductivity in granular silicon with Na atoms up to ~ 475 K is from ~ 10 V $\cdot$ k/mK to ~ 50 V $\cdot$ k/mK, in samples with Cs atoms, thermal conductivity is from ~ 20 V $\cdot$ k/mK to ~ 70 V $\cdot$ k/mK will change.[10-15]

Figure 2. Dependence of thermal conductivity on temperature:
1 – Si, 2 – Na, 3 – Cs atoms belong to the introduced granules.

It is known that the introduction of various inputs leads to changes in the thermal conductivity of semiconductor materials. For example, if the thermal conductivity of thermoelectric materials obtained by the powder method decreases due to external pressure, changing its composition due to the introduction of additional inputs can lead to an increase in thermal conductivity [1, 2]. In our case, the inclusion of alkali metal atoms in granulated silicon leads to an increase in thermal conductivity.

Conclusion

The efficiency of thermoelectric materials is directly proportional to the driving force and electrical conductivity, and inversely proportional to the thermal conductivity, and the increase in thermal conductivity has a negative effect on the efficiency of thermoelectric materials. However, as we have seen above, elimination of defects of alkali metal atoms in two adjacent areas in granulated silicon leads to an increase in electrical conductivity and a decrease in specific resistance up to 5÷8 times in accordance with the temperature. As a result, the results obtained in the study of the thermoelectric properties of granulated silicon can be important in obtaining new types of thermoelectric materials and explaining

the physical processes occurring in them.

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